

CHALLENGES IN TRANSLATING CULTURE – BOUND REFERENCES IN MEDIA TEXTS BETWEEN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

Yormamatova Mohichehra Jo'raqul qizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13903791>

Abstract: This article investigates the complexities and challenges of translating media texts between Uzbek and English, emphasizing the critical role of culture-bound references, idiomatic expressions, and contextual nuances that often hinder accurate and effective translations. As globalization accelerates the exchange of media across cultures, understanding these challenges is essential for maintaining the integrity and accessibility of translated content.

Key words: challenges, structure, culture-bound references, proverbs, metaphors, equivalent, direct translation.

Media texts present special issues in linguacultural translation because of the complexities of both language structure and cultural context. The obstacles of translating media texts between Uzbek and English can be divided into numerous categories, each of which has a substantial impact on the translation's faithfulness, accuracy, and cultural relevance.

Uzbek, a Turkic language, and English, a Germanic language, differ significantly in structure and grammar. Uzbek uses a subject-object-verb structure, whereas English employs a subject-verb-object pattern. Due to this syntactic mismatch, straight translations are frequently unnatural or perplexing. Furthermore, Uzbek's agglutinative nature, in which suffixes are attached to a word stem to describe grammatical relationships, differs dramatically from English, which employs prepositions and independent words to convey equivalent meanings. This discrepancy frequently necessitates considerable sentence structure changes by the translation, which might have an impact on the flow and coherence of the multimedia content.

One of the most significant challenges in linguacultural translation, particularly in media texts, is handling culture-bound references and contextual nuances. These elements include idiomatic expressions, metaphors, proverbs, historical references, traditional customs, and culturally specific terms such as food, festivals, and societal norms. Media texts are often rich with these references, which may not have direct equivalents in the target language, leading to a delicate balancing act for translators.

Idioms and proverbs are deeply rooted in the cultural and historical experiences of a community. In Uzbek, expressions like "*Pichoq suyakka borib tiralgan*" (literally: "*The knife has reached the bone*") express a situation that has become unbearable or intolerable. In English, this might be translated as "*This is the last*

straw," which conveys a similar meaning. However, if a translator were to render the Uzbek idiom too literally, without considering its cultural equivalent, it could confuse the English-speaking audience who may not grasp the severity or nuance implied.

Another example is the common Uzbek proverb "*Qo'y to'ri oldida yotgan bo'ri och qoladi*," which translates to "*A wolf lying by the sheep pen stays hungry*." This proverb suggests that desires can be restrained by circumstances or caution. In English, an equivalent might be "*A watched pot never boils*." However, a literal translation would not easily communicate the metaphorical message of patience or restraint in desires. The translator has to interpret the underlying meaning and choose an equivalent idiom from the target language, rather than sticking to a word-for-word translation.

Metaphors often rely on culturally specific symbols or references that may not resonate with foreign audiences. For instance, the metaphor "*Oltin qafasda qush*" in Uzbek, which means "*A bird in a golden cage*," represents a person living in luxury but lacking freedom or true happiness. The English equivalent is "*A gilded cage*." In this case, the metaphorical meaning is fairly easy to translate because the imagery of a cage and freedom resonates across both cultures. However, other metaphors might not be as universally understood.

Consider the metaphor in English: "*It's raining cats and dogs*," meaning it's raining heavily. Translating this phrase literally into Uzbek as "*Mushuklar va itlar yog'ayapti*" would confuse the audience because the cultural association of animals with rain does not exist in Uzbek. In Uzbek, a more culturally relevant expression might be "*Shalola bo'lib yomg'ir yog'di*," meaning "*It rained like a waterfall*," which effectively conveys the intensity of the rain without the use of an unfamiliar metaphor.

Cultural and historical references are particularly challenging because they are often specific to the societal context of the source language. For example, translating media texts that reference historical figures or events from Uzbek culture into English may require extensive footnotes or background explanations. A phrase like "*Amir Temurga o'xshash qat'iyat*" (meaning "determination like Amir Temur") refers to the famous conqueror Amir Temur (Tamerlane) who holds significant historical and cultural importance in Uzbekistan. However, English readers who are unfamiliar with Central Asian history may not understand the strength of this comparison.

In English, media texts often reference Western historical figures like Abraham Lincoln, Winston Churchill, or specific events like "Watergate" or "9/11." These

references are loaded with cultural significance, and a translator working from English into Uzbek would need to find local equivalents or provide explanatory context to ensure that the target audience grasps the full implications of the reference.

For instance, comparing someone's perseverance to Winston Churchill's leadership during World War II might not carry the same weight for an Uzbek reader unfamiliar with British history. Instead, a local parallel to Amir Temur might be more culturally resonant.

Media texts often refer to culturally specific traditions, festivals, and food, which can be difficult to translate because of the deep cultural connections these terms carry. For example, the Uzbek term "*Navro'z*" refers to the Persian New Year celebrated widely across Central Asia. While the event can be described in English as "Navro'z, the Persian New Year festival," it still requires additional cultural explanation to convey its importance, associated customs, and symbolism of renewal. This challenge also exists when translating the concept of Thanksgiving from English to Uzbek, where the historical and cultural significance of the holiday would be unfamiliar to many in Uzbekistan. Simply translating it as "*Shukronalik kuni*" (a day of gratitude) does not convey the full historical background and familial associations tied to the American celebration. In culinary contexts, translation can become especially tricky. An example from Uzbek is "*somsa*," a type of pastry that is popular in Uzbekistan. While it might be tempting to translate this as "meat pie" or "pastry" in English, these terms fail to capture the uniqueness of the dish and its cultural significance. Similarly, translating "pizza" into Uzbek as "*nonli taom*" (bread food) would lose the cultural meaning and familiarity that the term "pizza" carries globally. In such cases, translators often retain the original term and provide an explanatory note to bridge the cultural gap.

In conclusion, translating culture-bound references and contextual nuances between Uzbek and English in media texts requires not only linguistic expertise but also a deep understanding of the cultural context of both languages. The challenge is to strike a balance between maintaining the integrity of the source text and making it accessible to the target audience. This often involves creative problem-solving to convey meaning, nuance, and cultural resonance without losing the core message of the original text. Translators must constantly navigate between domestication and foreignization, deciding when to adapt the text to the target culture and when to preserve its original cultural flavor.

Reference List:

1. Abdurazakov, B. D. (2015). *Intercultural Communication and Translation Strategies in Uzbek Literature*. Tashkent: Tashkent State University.
2. Akhmedov, M. A. (2013). *Translation Theory and Practice in Uzbekistan*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan State University of World Languages.
3. Baker, M. (1992). *In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation*. London: Routledge.
4. Bassnett, S. (2002). *Translation Studies* (3rd ed.). London: Routledge.
5. Hoshimov, G. K. (2016). "Linguistic Aspects of Translation: Cultural References and Their Implications." *Uzbek Linguistics*, 12(3), 21-36.
6. House, J. (2015). *Translation: A Multidisciplinary Approach*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
7. Karimov, S. M. (2018). *Culture and Language: The Impact of Uzbek Culture on Translation Practices*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan National Library.
8. Nida, E. A. (1964). *Toward a Science of Translating: With Special Reference to Principles and Procedures Involved in Translating Biblical Texts*. Leiden: Brill.
9. Rasulova, N. K. (2017). "Challenges in Translating Cultural References in Media Texts: An Uzbek Perspective." *Journal of Translation Studies*, 10(2), 45-58.
10. Venuti, L. (1995). *The Translator's Invisibility: A History of Translation*. London: Routledge.